

KNOWLEDGE AND PRACTICE OF FOOD HYGIENE AMONG FOOD VENDORS IN KEFFI, NASARAWA STATE NIGERIA AND ITS IMPLICATION ON THEIR BUSINESS

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ABSTRACT

The high rate of food borne diseases have become a matter of public health concern with its resultant effect of increasing morbidity and mortality across the general population. Some of the cases of foodborne illness are traceable to pathogens from contaminated food and water consumption mostly at food vending sites. Street vended foods have become a booming business both in developed and developing countries mainly due to cost and convenience. This study was conducted to evaluate the Knowledge and Practice of food hygiene among food vendors in Keffi, North Central Region, Nigeria. The study engaged descriptive survey design and the population of the study was 586 food vendors in Keffi metropolis. The study through simple random sampling technique, adopted the use of self-structured questionnaire and interviews as the instrument for data collection. The data collected were analyzed using frequency counts and percentage. Findings of the study reveals that most food vendors in Keffi were female and persons whose age ranged between 21 and 40 years, with mainly secondary school education (71.0%) formed the bulk (66.0%) of person involved in this form of venture. The results from this study indicated that the food vendors in this study had poor knowledge of food safety and hygiene as their knowledge of transmission of food borne diseases, personal hygiene, contamination and cross- contamination as well as temperature regulations for food were inadequate. The level of practice of food hygiene was also observed to be inadequate. To reduce the incidences of foodborne diseases, this study recommended that proper monitoring and evaluation of the activities of food vendors should be conducted by officials of the Environmental and Public health departments of the local council authorities and regular training programmes should be conducted for food vendors to improve their knowledge of food safety and hygiene as well as proper food handing processes and procedures. This will ultimately improve their business and enhance the business administration ability.

Keywords: *Business; Contaminant; Disinfection; Establishment; Food-Hygiene*

INTRODUCTION

Food vendors are known to provide ready-made meals that are relatively affordable, easily accessible in unconventional places for the marginal people in developing countries. As stated by DeWaal and Rober (2023), the act of food vending has become a booming business and a source of daily income for a good number of people especially in developing countries. In the face of unabating unemployment and economic downturn in most developing countries, many young people especially women have joined the bandwagon of food vendors basically for survival. Most of these people do not have basic training in food safety and hygiene which has become a major issue in recent times.

Food safety and hygiene are currently a major issue of global public health concern especially in developing countries due to increasing food-borne diseases (FBDs) that can lead to morbidity and mortality, and concomitant effects on trade and development (WHO,2023). They further reported that this concern is heightened by the fact that, worldwide, there seems to be a change in life-style and food consumption patterns as frequency of “eating out” is increasing and commitment to food preparation at home is decreasing most probably do to the increase in schedules and activities.

While Osaili et al., (2018) posited that food safety continues as a critical problem in developed and developing nations for people, food companies and food control officials Nyenje & Ndip, (2018) emphasized that food-borne illnesses are common among vulnerable groups, such as infants, young children, elderly and the immune-compromised. In spite of efforts made to contain the issue of food safety and environment, Sabir et al., (2018) reported that 2.1 million adults and three million children, including two million in developing countries, die each year from water consumption or contaminated food while WHO (2012) indicated that up to 1.5 billion episodes of diarrhoea and more than three million deaths occur in children every year due to food and water contamination and an estimated 600 million world population, about 1 in 10 people fall sick after eating contaminated food and 420,000 die every year. They also reported that 40 per cent of children under 5 years of age bear the burden of food-borne disease, with 125,000 deaths every year

From the assessment of Onyenero and Hedberg (2013), food safety problems generally centre on foodborne diseases which are basically associated with poor hygiene and are largely connected with eating of contaminated food and water. As opined by Tomaszewska et al (2018), foodborne disease have become a significant public health challenge with medical care costs, inferior quality of life (comprising of lowered labour productivity) and decreased life expectancy consequences. They also indicate that foodborne outbreaks is very uncommon in well-established hotels and restaurants; as such, it is predominantly associated eating of cheap street-vended foods that are prepared with reduced care and poor food hygiene measures. They are thus linked with preparation and selling food under insanitary conditions, inadequate access to potable water, sanitary or waste disposal services.

As suggested by Tomaszewska et al, (2018), reducing the consequences of foodborne diseases depends significantly on improved food hygiene practice by food vendor, the conduct of customers/food handlers when procuring food as well as their attitude towards food safety and hygiene during food preparation. They further opined that in sub-Saharan Africa, foodborne disease outbreaks are associate with inadequate individual hygiene of street food vendors and food handlers in food settings.

So much emphasis is placed on food safety that necessitated the formulation of a general principle of food hygiene by the World Health Organization (WHO) in 2007. The recommended principle basically are:

1. Prevent contaminating food with pathogens spreading from people, pets and pests.
2. Separate raw from cooked foods to prevent contaminating the cooked food.
3. Cook food for the appropriate length of time and at the appropriate temperature to kill pathogens.
4. Store food at the proper temperature.
5. Use safe water and raw materials.

Street-vended foods might cause major health problems due to absence of basic facilities and services, such as safe water provisions, their short duration nature, and insufficient knowledge of basic food safety measures. It is therefore the purpose of the study to examine the knowledge of street food vendors of these recommended standards and how their ability to administer their business to proper evaluate the health implication of this practice on the population.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

Food is a basic necessity and critical for the physical wellbeing and survival of both humans and animals. However, the processes involved in its handling, preparation, production and consumption is essential effective life sustenance. Therefore, it is important that it be properly handled and safe guarded to avoid contamination along the along the food chain to avoid fatal consequences. Street food vending has become a major constitute in the food chain as it provides a source of convenient, mostly affordable, easily accessible food. They also serve as a source of income for vendors in the face of current economic realities.

As averred by Asiegbu, et al (2016), street foods include ready- to- eat foods and beverages prepared which are sold by vendors in streets and other public places for immediate consumption or consumption at a later time without further processing or preparation. For clarity, a food vendor is any person who handles food, by either preparing, selling or both. This group of people play important roles in food safety to limit the contamination of food substances and materials along the food during production, processing, distribution and serving (Mamun and Turin, 2016).

Therefore, the understanding of food safety procedures and the potential factors that causes food borne diseases is very essential for all those involved in food vending as they are estimated to be patronized by about 2.5 billion people globally (WHO, 2015). As such, they reported that food contamination creates an enormous social and economic burden on communities and their health systems.

JUSTIFICATION OF STUDY

Although the global incidence of foodborne disease is difficult to estimate, globally, food contamination has generated an enormous social and economic burden on communities and their health systems. Food hygiene is therefore a concern not only to developing countries but also to

developed countries as a result of its devastating implications. According to the WHO and Centre for Disease Control (CDC), in the USA alone annually there are 76 million cases of foodborne illnesses leading to 325,000 hospitalization and 5,000 deaths and an outbreak of Hepatitis A, resulting from the consumption of contaminated clams, affected some 300,000 individuals in China (WHO,2007). Though not well documented, developing countries are believed to bear the brunt of food contamination due to the presence of a wide range of foodborne diseases, including those caused by parasites as the high prevalence of diarrhoeal disease in many developing countries suggests major underlying food safety problems (WHO, 2007).

According to Nyamagwa (2020), food prepared and vended on the streets in Kenya, Uganda, Ghana and Nigeria posed health hazards because most food vendors are not aware of the risk of unhygienic practices and that they do not observe the hygiene control practices. It is therefore important to examine the knowledge of food vendors of the recommended standards for proper food handling, how well they practice these recommendations and its implication on effective business administration.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The objectives of the study were to evaluate the knowledge of food vendors on basic food hygiene practices and how well they abide by these practices in their food handling processes.

The specific objectives are:

1. To assess the level of knowledge of food hygiene among the food handlers in Keffi;
2. To assess the attitude of food handlers towards food hygiene;
3. To assess the practice of food hygiene among food vendors;
4. To evaluate the relation between the knowledge of basic food safety measure and the practice of food hygiene among food vendors.
5. Evaluate how their knowledge of food hygiene impact on their ability to manage their business

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Some of the questions designed to effectively guide this study include;

1. How much knowledge and awareness does the food vendors in Keffi have about food hygiene?
2. What is the underlying factor behind food vending among food vendors in Keffi?
3. What is the relationship between knowledge of food safety and the practice of food hygiene among food vendors in Keffi?
4. What factors make the practice of food hygiene among food vendors effective/ineffective at the rural level?
5. How can these barriers be eliminated to improve proper handling of food and ultimately reduce food contamination in Nigeria?
6. How can this study be leveraged on to enhance food safety and business management ability

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Findings from this study will potentially contribute to the following:

1. Facilitate the implementation of best practice among food vendors.

2. Provide information to enhance food safety.
3. Appraise and identify some of the factors militating against food hygiene.
4. Make evidence- based recommendations on how food safety awareness and campaigns and interventions can be improved to become more result oriented in the effective management of their business.
5. Objectively highlight areas where further research may be required to improve food safety and enhanced health outcomes.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The focus of this study is principally evaluate the knowledge of food hygiene among food vendors, how it affects the overall food safety practices to prevent the outbreak foodborne diseases in Nigeria and their business management ability.

METHODOLOGY

Food hygiene has become an issue of public health concern in recent time as Governments across the world as well as local and international agencies all over the world are intensifying efforts to improve food hygiene as ensure food safety (Alimi, 2016). These efforts are not unconnected with the increasing reports of the widespread challenges of food-borne illness (Doyle and Erickson;2021). Also there is the need to response to the increasing number of food safety problems and rising consumer concerns about food safety and quality; and demand more transparency in production and distribution as WHO (2012) indicated that up to 1.5 billion episodes of diarrhoea and more than three million deaths occur in children every year due to food and water contamination and an estimated 600 million world population, about 1 in 10 people fall sick after eating contaminated food and 420,000 die every year. They also reported that 40 per cent of children under 5 years of age bear the burden of food-borne disease, with 125,000 deaths every year. Furthermore, a proper understanding of food hygiene among these category of small business owners could enhance their business.

Therefore, to effectively carry out this study, the methodology adopted incorporated issues ranging from the research setting, study design, study population, sampling procedure, research instrument to data collection and statistical analysis.

RESEARCH SETTING

This study was conducted in Keffi. Keffi is a town in Nasarawa State, North Central Nigeria. Its headquarters are in the town of Keffi. It is 50 kilometers from Abuja. It has an area of 138 km² and a population of about 92,664 at the 2006 census (www.britannica.com,2022). It is home to a university, Nasarawa State University, three colleges of health Technology, a federal medical centre, a general hospital, two primary healthcare centres, various private health facilities numerous primary and post primary institutions

STUDY DESIGN

A descriptive cross section study approach was engaged in this study to evaluate the knowledge and hygiene practices among street food vendors in the preparation and handling of food.

STUDY POPULATION

The study population comprises food handlers who operate restaurants and open vending of food in keffi and their staff.

Inclusion Criteria

- All restaurants and open food vendors in Keffi were targeted.
- All managers/manageress of restaurants within Keffi were targeted
- All the cooks, stewards/stewardesses, those who go to purchase food items for each of the restaurant and food vendors within Keffi were targeted.

A study population of 586 persons were involved in this study drawn from the above targets.

RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

The following tools were employed to collect data from eligible respondents.

- **Questionnaire:** it contained mostly structured close-ended questions with few open-ended questions. It was used to collect information from each respondent on knowledge, and practice of food hygiene. The first part of the questionnaire was on socio-demographics while the later part covers questions on knowledge of food hygiene, attitude towards hygiene, and practice of hygiene, in food handling. The questionnaires were administered by interviewer.
- **An observational checklist:** this was used to assess the level of food hygiene practices of each of the eating establishment

DATA COLLECTION

The questionnaires were randomly distributed among Participants within the area of study. The respondents were given enough time to provide their opinion on the issues raised in the questionnaire objectively and the use of interviews were also engaged to help some participants complete the questionnaire. The observation checklist was quietly completed.

DATA ANALYSIS

The data obtained were collected, collated and analysed using frequency and percentage tables for easy understanding.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATION

Ethical approval was obtained from the Environmental and Public health departments of the Keffi local government area of Nasarawa State before the study commenced. Each participant was clearly informed on the content and context of the study for consent and participation was voluntary

RESULT

The results obtained from the study are highlighted below. The results are presented in frequency and percentage tables for clarity and easy understanding.

SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF RESPONDENTS

The socio-demographic characteristic of the respondents is as presented in table 1 below.

TABLE 1: SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF RESPONDENTS

VARIABLE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
GENDER		
Male	106	18.1
Female	480	81.9
AGE (YEARS)		
Below 20	102	17.4
21-30	206	35.1
31-40	181	30.9
41-50	72	12.3
50 and above	25	4.3
MARITAL STATUS		
Married	511	65.5
Single	126	16.2
Divorced	121	15.5
Separated	22	2.8
Education Level		
Primary	112	19.1
Secondary	416	7.0
Tertiary	58	9.9
NO OF YEARS IN THE FOOD VENDING BUSINESS		
Below 1 year	136	23.2
1-5	241	41.1
6-10	102	17.4
10-15	97	16.6
16 and above	10	1.7
REASONS FOR BEING IN THE FOOD VENDING BUSINESS		

Earn Income	315	53.7
Person Interest	106	18.1
No other option	131	22.4
Inheritance	34	5.8
TRAINING ON FOOD HANDLING		
YES	106	18.1
NO	480	81.9

The table showed that five hundred and eight six respondents were involved in this study. 18.1% of them were males while 81.9 % of them were females. 83.4% of the respondents were 40 years and below while 16.6% of them were above 40 years of age. While 19.1 % of the respondents had their highest level of education pegged at primary school, a greater portion of them (80.9%) had at least secondary level of education.

While 23.2% of the respondents have been in the food vending business for below 1 year, 41.1% have been there between 1 and 5 years, 37.4% for between 6 and 10 years, 16.6% for between 10 and 15 years while only 1.7% of them have been in the business for over 15 years.

In all, 53.7% of the respondents were in the food vending business to earn income, 18.1% on personal interest, 22.4% are there because they do not have other options yet while 5.8% of the respondents simply inherited the food vending business. Among the respondents, only 18.1% have received some form of training on food handling while 81.9% do not have any form of official training on food handling.

KNOWLEDGE ON FOOD SAFETY

The knowledge of respondents on food safety and hygiene was assessed using four critical food safety factors; knowledge on transmission of food borne diseases, knowledge on personal hygiene, knowledge on contamination and cross-contamination, and knowledge on temperature control as opined by Funmilola et al, (2018).

Respondents' knowledge on food safety and hygiene are presented in table 2.

TABLE 2: RESPONDENTS KNOWLEDGE ON FOOD SAFETY AND HYGIENE

Variable	Agree		Disagree		I don't Know	
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
Transmission of Food Borne Diseases						
• Fresh eggs could have salmonella (a. bacteria)	156	26.6	251	42.8	179	30.5
• Fresh meat could have micos on the surface	135	23.0	318	54.3	133	22.7
• People looking healthy could carry germs	118	20.1	342	58.4	126	21.5
• Food saved cold (salads) could not be contaminated	323	55.1	216	36.9	47	8.0
• Some raw vegetables like lettuce could contain harmful bacteria	218	37.2	316	53.9	52	8.9
• Cooked food cannot have microbes	314	53.6	101	17.2	171	29.2
Personal Hygiene						
• It is not necessary to wash your hands regularly when serving cooked food	106	18.1	344	58.7	136	23.2
• As long as you wear gloves, you can handle cooked food and raw meat at the same time	119	20.3	216	36.9	251	42.8
• It is necessary to wash your hands after every visit to the toilet or restroom	398	68.0	142	24.2	46	7.8
	326	55.6	114	19.5	46	7.9

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> It is important to wash your hands after every visit to the toilet or restroom 	196	33.4	348	59.4	42	7.2
Cross Contamination						
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Food borne diseases can be caused by storing cooked food and raw meat in the same refrigerator 	216	36.9	296	50.5	74	12.6
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Food can be contaminated with microbes when in contact with unsafe food 	291	49.7	261	44.5	34	5.8
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Food can be contaminated from food preparation surfaces 	209	35.7	294	50.2	83	14.1
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> After preparing meat you can cut ready to eat food (vegetables on the same surface) 	394	67.2	188	32.1	4	0,7
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Soap and water can be help to reduce food cross contamination 	211	36.0	249	42.5	126	21.5
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ready to eat food can be contaminated when stored together with raw food. 						
Temperature Regulation	485	82.8	101	17.2	----	---
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Leftover food should be reheated to a minimum temperature of 75C 	101	17.2	196	33.5	289	49.3
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Foods that needs to be kept warm should be at 60C or above 	509	86.9	----	----	77	13.1
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Microbes can grow in leftover food stored at room temperature 	511	87.2	52	8.9	23	3.9
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cooked food should be stored in the refrigerator at 5C 	492	84.0	53	9.0	41	7.0
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All bacteria that can cause food borne illness are destroyed when food is stored in the refrigerator 	305	52.0	211	36.0	70	12.0
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Food borne illness causing microbes grow well in room temperature 	218	37.2	209	35.7	159	27.1

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Frozen food should be thawed (melted) on the counter or in the sink 						
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Table 2 indicated that 42.8% disagreed that fresh eggs could have bacteria, while 30.5% do not know. 54.3% disagreed that fresh meat could have microbes while 22.7% do not know. 58.4% also disagreed that canned food may have harmful microbes. 21.3% do not know. Also, 55-1% believe that people looking healthy cannot carry germs while 44.0% agreed that food served cold like salads could not be contaminated. Also, regarding the transmission of foodborne diseases, 53.6% agreed that cooked food cannot have microbes.

On the knowledge of respondents on personal hygiene, 68.0% of the respondents agreed that it is necessary to wash your hands after sneezing or coughing and 55.6 % also agreed that it is important to wash your hands after visiting the toilet or rest room.

Regarding contamination and cross-contamination, 49.7% agreed that food can be contaminated during preparation while 67.2% agreed that soap and water can help in reducing cross contamination.

On the knowledge on temperature regulations for food, 82.8% agreed that left over food should be re-heated to a minimum of 75^oc and 86.9% opined that microbes can grow in leftover food stored at room temperature. Also, 87.2% agreed that cooked food should be stored in the refrigerator at a temperature of 5^oc while 84.0% agreed that all bacteria that cause foodborne illnesses are destroyed when food is store in the refrigerator and 52.0% of the respondents agreed that foodborne illnesses causing microbes grow ell at room temperature.

HYGIENE PRACTICE AMONG FOOD VENDORS

Hygiene practices among food vendors are as highlighted in table 3.

TABLE 3: FOOD HYGIENE PRACTICE AMONG FOOD VENDORS

VARIABLE	ALWAYS		SOMETIMES		NEVER	
	FREQUENCY	%	FREQUENCY	%	FREQUENCY	%
• Do you wash your hands before unwrapping raw food?	108	18.4	196	33.5	282	48.1
• Do you wash your hands after unwrapping raw food?	108	18.4	196	33.5	282	48.1
• Do you wash your hands before touching cooked food?	95	16.2	106	18.1	385	65.7
• Do you wash your hands after touching cooked food?	115	19.6	121	20.7	350	59.7
• Do you separate utensils when preparing raw and cooked food?	56	9.6	138	23.5	392	66.9
• Do you thaw (melt) frozen foods at room temperature?	191	32.6	132	22.5	263	44.9
• Do you check expiry date of product?	98	16.7	153	26.1	335	57.2
• Do you use gloves when sewing unwrapped food?	151	25.8	139	23.7	296	50.5
• Do you wash your hands after using gloves?	107	12.3	88	15.0	391	66.7

• Do you wear apron when serving food?	118	20.1	92	15.7	376	64.2
• Do you come to work ill with a fever, running stomach or diarrhea?	394	67.2	110	18.8	86	14.7
• Do you use a handkerchief when suffering from a cold?	199	34.0	156	26.6	231	39.4
• Do you cover your hair when cooking or serving food?	101	34.3	121	20.6	264	45.1
• Do you disinfect cutting board after each use?	102	17.4	96	16.4	388	66.2
• Do you use kitchen towel to dry utensils?	98	10.7	151	25.8	337	57.2

From table 3, majority of the respondents do not practice regular hand washing during preparation and serving of food. Also, most of them (66.9%) do not separate utensils between raw and cooked food. Similarly, 57.2% of them do not check the expiring date of purchased food materials before using them for food preparation, 50.5% do not use hand gloves when serving food and 66.7% do not think it is important to wash your hands after using hand gloves. Furthermore, 64.2% of the respondents do not wear aprons when serving food and 67.2% come to work and participate in cooking and serving food when ill with fever, running stomach or diarrhea. 66.2% of the respondents do not disinfect cutting board after each use while 57.5% do not use clean kitchen towers to dry utensils.

OBSERVED FOOD HYGIENE PRACTICE AMONG FOOD VENDORS

The observed food hygiene practices among food vendors during the study are as highlighted in table 4.

TABLE 4: OBSERVED FOOD HYGIENE PRACTICES AMONG FOOD VENDORS

VARIABLE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGES
1. Adequate protection of food from dust YES	388	66.2

NO	198	33.8
2. Dishing out food with spoons/candles		
YES	386	100
NO	----	-----
3. Finger Nails		
clean	708	35.5
unclean	378	64.5
4. Hair protection		
Present	186	31.7
Absent	400	68.3
5. Use of Apron		
YES	210	37.2
NO	376	64.2

Table 4 revealed that though 100% of the respondents dish out food with spoons and ladles, only 66.2% of the respondents adequately protected the food they vend from flies and dust. Similarly, 64.5% had unclean finger nails, 68.3 did not cover their hair and 64.2% did not wear apron when serving food.

DISCUSSION

This study was designed to evaluate the knowledge of food vendors on food safety and hygiene and how they explore the concepts of food hygiene in the practice of their trade. The findings from this study revealed the following as the basic factors;

SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS

Most of the food vendors were between the ages of 20 and 40 years which is similar to earlier findings in the study by Trafialek, et al (2017) in which 50.0% of the food vendors were aged 25–35 years. Also, the overwhelming majority of female food vendors in this study corroborates the observation of Okojie (2014). This can be alluded to the fact that women are nature responsible for cooking for the family especially in developing countries, a situation that makes females more associated with food vending than males.

With respect to educational qualification, most of the respondents in this study have attained secondary level of education (71.0%), a finding similar to that of Chukueze (2020). This is supposed to help them clearly understand the basic principle of food safety and hygiene in order to enhance their practice of the essential processes and procedure involved in safe food preparation and storage. Previous studies have also reported similar finding that educational level of food vendors was significantly related to food safety and hygiene practices of the food vendors (Oladoyinbo et al, 2015; Tolulope et al, 2015). The low participation of graduates of tertiary

education in food vending could be linked to the belief that they have better opportunities for employment in the formal sector.

Also, majority of the respondents (53.7%) are the food vending business simply to earn income and not because of interest (18.1%). This suggests that their commitment to good practices will be limited as they to result in any form of malpractices to enhance their income, furthermore, a very high percentage of respondents (81.9 %) have not attended any form of training on food handling processes. This is quite high when compared to reports from other studies (Zain, et al 2012; and Kibret and Abere, 2012). As such, their practices are not based on any solid background as Mizanur et al. (2012) established that training in food safety significantly increased food safety practice among food handlers.

This study thus implies that the level of education of respondents and previous training on food safety could affects their food hygiene and safety practices. Therefore, food handlers will benefit from regular training programmes on food handling processes and procedures to enhance their food safety practices and the potentials of their business.

KNOWLEDGE OF RESPONDENTS ON FOOD SAFETY AND HYGIENE

According to Akabande et al, (2017), knowledge of food vendors about the food borne infections and food safety practices is important to reduce the outbreaks of food borne infection and promote their business.

This study revealed that on the average, only about a quarter of the participants had adequate knowledge on the transmission of food-borne diseases as about 26.6% of them agreed that fresh eggs could have salmonella, and 23.0% also agreed that fresh meat always have microbes on the surface though 55.1% agreed that healthy people could also transmit germs to food and 53.6% agreed that cooked food can have microbes. This could be associated with the fact that most of the participants (81.9%) do not have any formal or informal training on food safety and its implication on their business.

Also, result from this study as indicated in table 2 revealed that the knowledge of respondents on contamination and cross-contamination of food was generally not adequate as only 33.4% of the respondents agreed that food borne diseases could result from storing raw meat and cooked food in the same refrigerator and 36.9% also believed that food can be contaminated with microbes when in contact with unsafe foods. However, about 49.7% of the respondents agreed that food can be contaminated from food preparation surfaces and 67.2% also believed that the use of soap and water can help reduce food cross contamination.

Findings as contained in table 2 also showed that most of the respondents have relatively a low understanding of ideal temperature regulations for food substances. This is in line with earlier findings reported by Funmilola et al, (2018). The role temperature regulation using the refrigeration process in the preservation of food is essential to ensuring food safety. Finding from this study thus suggests that only a few of the food handlers in Keffi can effectively store food by refrigeration. This implies the possibility of a high rate of food contamination during storage among the study population.

The knowledge of proper personal hygiene was also revealed from the findings of this study to be low among the respondents. 18.1% of the respondents agreed that it is not necessary to wash your hands regularly when serving cooked food, 68.0% agreed that it is not necessary to wash your hand after sneezing or coughing and only 55.6% agreed that it is important to wash your hand after every visit to the toilet or rest room. This could be associated with the low level of training on the handling of food materials.

FOOD HYGIENE PRACTICES AMONG FOOD VENDORS

Findings from this study as indicated in table 3, showed that food hygiene practices among the respondents was very poor as only about 20% of them showed good conduct across all the parameter used in this study. Also, observation of the respondents during the study as indicated in table 4, showed that just about 35% of the respondents displayed good food hygiene practices in the conduct of their food vending activities. These findings corroborate to certain extents with the report of Tolulope et al, (2015). The poor practice of food hygiene among food vendors could negative impact on their business as any outbreak of food-borne disease around the business enterprise adversely affect the business.

CONCLUSION

Outbreak of food borne diseases can occur due to food contamination resulting from poor food handling by food vendors especially in developing nations like Nigeria where there are weak regulations. The study assessed knowledge of food safety and hygiene practice among food vendors in Keffi. Findings from this study showed that food borne illness are the product of poor knowledge of food safety among respondents and poor food hygiene practices. As earlier stated, this trend could negatively affect their business.

RECOMMENDATIONS

From the foregoing the following suggestions are recommended to ensure that people who patronize food vendors eat good and quality food to prevent the outbreak of food borne diseases:

- Regular training programmes should be conducted by the environmental and public health departments of the local government council for food vendors on environmental, food and personal hygiene.
- Food vendors should be enlightened on safe food preparation methods by NGOs and other relevant agencies.
- Regular monitoring and evaluation of the activities of food vendors should be conducted by relevant agencies.
- Only approved locations should be used for food vending to reduce the possibilities of food contamination.
- Local council authorities should ensure the enforcement of regulations and laws on food safety and hygiene
- Food vendors should be properly licensed before they commence operation in order to regulate their activities.
- Food vendors should be aware that poor understanding and practice of food hygiene could negative impact on their business.

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

Due to time and funding constraints this study was limited only Keffi metropolis. It will be a worthwhile experience to extend this study to the outskirts of the town for a more comprehensive study.

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